

Data set of measurement data vs test conditions for IT performance characterised in presence of separate and combined influence factors

Partner	PTB
Measured power quality parameter	Ratio errors and phase displacement
Influence factor 1	Adjacent phases
Influence factor 2 (if combined with 1)	Position effects
Influence factor 3 (if combined with 2 and 3)	-
Index used to compare the reference power quality parameter with the measured power quality parameter	Ratio error defined as $\varepsilon = \frac{k_n U_s - U_p}{U_p}$ $\delta = \varphi_s - \varphi_p$
Transducer under test	<p>Inductive CT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rated primary current 500 A • Rated scale factor 500A/A • Rated burden 2.5VA • Accuracy class 0.5 <p align="center"><i>Fig 1: Photo of the device under test (DUT) CT</i></p>
Measurement procedure (short description)	<p>Tests for position effects deal with four aspects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Centring 2. Connector position of the CTs; 3. Distance d between the primary conductor through DUT and its return conductor; 4. Repeatability / Random. <p>The tests of adjacent phases were performed including the three aspects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Connector position of the CTs; 3. Distance d between the primary conductor through DUT and its return conductor; 4. Repeatability / Random. <p>For centring test, as depicted in Figure 2.</p>

Fig 2: Position of centring

The measurements were conducted at five positions (A, B, C, D, E) for the primary conductor of the CT.

For the connector position and distance tests, the laboratory measurement setup shown in Figure 3 involved testing at four positions (0°, 90°, 180°, 270°) for the connector placement.

Fig 3: Instruction of connector, primary conductor and return conductor

The distance d between the primary conductor through the DUT and its return conductor was set between 5 cm and 50 cm. In all tests, the primary current I_P was set to a sinusoidal waveform at power frequency with a current of 100 A. The default setup parameters are primary conductor at position A; connector position at 270°; $d = 50$ cm. To validate the repeatability of the measurements, at least 7 measurements were repeated with the default setups for the DUT CT.

Measurement Setup (short description)

The setups of the reference system for current sensor calibrations at power frequency and for the wideband frequencies are illustrated in Figure 4.

The calibration system is mainly composed of a current generation system (marked as red block), a set of reference CTs with associated precision resistors (marked as green blocks in the path N), the DUT (DUT I and DUT II, marked as yellow blocks in the path X) and a high precision 2-channel ratioed voltage measuring system (MS, marked as grey block).

The PTB laboratory measurement setup is presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Main results (tables, plots,...)

The maximum difference of the DUT errors at 50 Hz with nominal burden by various tests for position effects is listed in Table 1. The centring of the primary conductor has a dominant effect in position effects.

Table 1. Maximum difference of ratio and phase errors at 50 Hz with rated burden by various tests for position effects (primary current $I_p = 100$ A).

	$\Delta\varepsilon$ (%)	$\Delta\delta$ (crad)
1. Centring	0.04	0.02
2. Connector position of the CTs;	0.01	0
3. Distance d between the primary conductor through DUT and its return conductor;	0.01	0
4. Repeatability / Random.	0.02	0.03

To test the adjacent effects without using a practical 3-phase current system, the DUT CT were tested without primary input for the DUT CT and with 100 A primary input for the reference CT. In this case, the measured DUT errors \underline{E}_x can be considered as results caused by adjacent effects. Additionally, the evaluation was first focused on the ratio errors. Finally, the obtained ratio errors E are applied to all angles, $\underline{E} = \underline{E}_x / U_{N,S\text{-rated}} \cdot U_{X,S\text{-rated}}$, where $U_{N,S\text{-rated}}$ and $U_{X,S\text{-rated}}$ respectively represent the rated secondary voltage of the reference CT and the DUT CT. As a result, the maximum difference of the ratio errors $\Delta|\underline{E}|$ or the maximum ratio errors $|\underline{E}|_{\max}$ at 50 Hz with nominal burden by various tests for adjacent effects are summarised in Table 2. The connector position of the primary conductor has a dominant effect in adjacent effects.

Table 2. Results at 50 Hz with rated burden by various tests for adjacent effects ($I_p = 100$ A).

	$\Delta E $ in %
2. Connector position of the CTs;	0.03
3. Distance d between the primary conductor through DUT and its return conductor;	0.01
	$ E _{\max}$ in %
4. Repeatability / Random.	0.009

References

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Attached files

Name: 19NRM05_CT_PTB.zip

Description: It contains 2 excel data:

- one for the proximity test (External_Position);
- one for the adjacent phases test (External_Adjacent_Phases).

One excel (External_Position) includes 5 worksheet: information of the DUT CT; results of 1. Centring; results of 2. Connector position of the CTs; results of 3. Distance d

	<p>between the primary conductor through DUT and its return conductor; results of 4. Repeatability / Random.</p> <p>One excel (External_Adjacent_Phases) includes 4 worksheet: information of the DUT CT; results of 2. Connector position of the CTs; results of 3. Distance d between the primary conductor through DUT and its return conductor; results of 4. Repeatability / Random.</p> <p>All the results were acquired from a precision two channel ratioed voltage measuring system for 1 s with a sampling frequency of $f_s=50$ kHz.</p>
<p>Agree to make the data public ? (yes/no)</p>	<p>yes</p>